

Data Analytics Centre

KPFI – LEIF

Energy & Investment Efficiency Analysis

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CASE DESCRIPTION

Case description:

1. Given building innovation data → Assess *the Energy Efficiency* (EE) & *Investment Efficiency* (IE).
2. Identify *patterns* in the outcomes of current EE Investments.
3. Provide a *predictive model* for incoming investment proposals.

RAW DATA PROCESSING & ASSUMPTIONS -1

- ❑ Initial sample size: 550
- ❑ Multiple projects have no baseline year. A baseline year is necessary to compare the energy consumption before and after an innovation project. We excluded these projects from our analysis.
- ❑ 498 out of 550 project have baseline year
- ❑ Few projects, out of 498 with baseline year, have negative % of Energy Reduction, which means that the energy consumption increased. This is due to increased Electricity Consumption (change in Energy Consumption pattern by the users). We excluded these projects from our analysis.
- ❑ Finally, **our analysis is based on 485 out of 550 projects.**

RAW DATA PROCESSING & ASSUMPTIONS -2

- ❑ There are multiple reporting years after each project. For our analysis, we compare the closest reporting year to the end date of each project and afterwards we compare this year with the baseline year. By doing so, we quarantine that there is no significant variation in the weather conditions and the building utilization before and right after the project.
- ❑ This **assumption** can be further improved by introducing to our analysis the rests of the reporting years and the notion of heating degree days. **However**, in that case, we cannot do anything when we have significant changes in buildings' utilization (e.g. increasing electricity consumption). Therefore, we avoided to introduce the rests of reporting years.

SAMPLE DATA ANALYSIS -1

Final metrics per project to analyse:

Project No.	Total project costs (€)	Grant financing (€)	Grand/Total cost (%)	Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)	% Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)
KPFI-1/1	367,882.94	290,627.53	79	111.29	54
KPFI-1/10	1,226,770.81	1,042,755.19	85	110.75	59
KPFI-1/11	123,349.26	165,496.23	134	86.64	41
KPFI-1/12	273,418.26	218,734.61	80	160.29	70
KPFI-1/13	396,496.04	337,021.63	85	176.16	56
KPFI-1/14	140,815.76	119,693.40	85	46.79	24
KPFI-1/15	1 850 566 56	1 461 947 58	79	161 60	69

SAMPLE DATA ANALYSIS -2

Energy Reduction Distribution for all 485 sample projects:

MEAN:	52.04
Sample SD:	21.19
MEDIAN	53.04
SKEW:	-0.23
Min:	0.00
Max:	100.00

SAMPLE DATA ANALYSIS -3

% of Grand Financing vs % Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)

Conclusion: It seems that there is lack of specific rule/pattern in LEIF project *funding procedure*. An ascending linear relationship might be more efficient

PEARSON:	-0.013
SPEARMAN:	-0.019

SAMPLE DATA ANALYSIS -4

- There is a similar pattern with previous plot, which support the previous conclusion

LABELING – PROPOSED GRAND FINANSING PLAN PER LABEL

Percentile (inclusive)	Histogram Bar Bounds of % Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)	# of projects	LABEL	PROPOSED Grand Financing (%)
20%	(0, 34.87]	97	poor	10
40%	(34.87, 48.87]	97	descent	30
60%	(48.87, 58.20]	96	good	50
80%	(58.20, 69.80]	97	very good	70
100%	(69.80, 100.00]	97	excellent	90

Histogram: No. of project per label

➤ We propose 5 labels → One % of Grand Financing per label.

The effect of **PROPOSED** Grand Financing Plan -1

Before

Grand Financing (€) vs % Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)

After

PROPOSED Grand Financing (€) vs % of Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)

Undesired region: Low % energy reduction & high financing cost

The effect of **PROPOSED** Grand Financing Plan -2

Before

After

% of Grand Financing vs % Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)

PROPOSED % of Grand Financing vs % Energy reduction (Kwh/m2)

There is a clear pattern

The effect of **PROPOSED** Grand Financing Plan -3

➤ The *total savings* (:484 projects) if the predictive model was 100% successful (best case scenario):

TOTAL GRAND FINANCING COST (€)
141,682,249
TOTAL PROPOSED GRAND FINANCING COST (€)
126,046,444
TOTAL SAVINGS (€)
15,635,806 €
TOTAL SAVINGS (%)
11%

To further improve the outcome (**11%**), we need to apply another grand financing plan, other than the proposed one.

Predictive model:
Ordinal logistic regression

RESULTS

TO BE CONTINUED

Thank you!

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